

STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CORONAL MASS EJECTIONS AND SOLAR ENERGETIC PARTICLES FOR X-CLASS SOLAR FLARES

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Abstract:

This study investigates the relationship between solar energetic particles (SEPs) and coronal mass ejections (CMEs) during Solar Cycle 24. It utilizes satellite data from SOHO and GOES, along with Python-based analytical tools. The study begins with an overview of the Sun's structure, including the core, radiative zone, and convective zone, and explains how the solar magnetic field and sunspots contribute to solar events like flares and CMEs. It reviews how CME shocks accelerate solar particles and their effects on Earth. The analysis covers CME velocity, mass, and kinetic energy, and identifies factors that influence particle acceleration. Findings reveal a strong correlation between CME velocity and density, with recent analyses discussed. The study offers recommendations for future research to improve prediction models for solar energetic events and reduce their impacts on technology, such as communication systems and satellites. It underscores the complex relationship between SEPs and CMEs, providing insights to enhance predictions and minimize their detrimental effects on critical technology.

Keywords: *Coronal mass ejections, solar energetic particles, Solar Flares, X-Class, CMEs, SEPs.*

Introduction

Introduction:

The sun, while an ordinary star among the roughly 100 billion stars in our galaxy, the Milky Way, is vital to the existence of life on Earth. It significantly impacts our planet by driving weather systems, regulating ocean currents, dictating seasonal changes, and influencing the climate. Moreover, the sun's energy is essential for photosynthesis, the process that sustains plant life and, by extension, the entire food chain. Beyond these immediate effects, the sun also plays a key role in maintaining the Earth's atmosphere and protecting us from harmful cosmic radiation through its solar wind and magnetic field. Without the sun's heat, light, and protective influence, life as we know it would not

exist on Earth. Furthermore, understanding solar phenomena like solar energetic particles (SEPs) and coronal mass ejections (CMEs) is essential for comprehending the sun's broader influence. Without the sun's heat, light, and protective effects, life as we know it on Earth would not be possible [1]. Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) release vast amounts of matter and magnetic flux from the Sun's atmosphere into the solar wind and interplanetary space. This ejected matter is a plasma primarily composed of electrons and protons, embedded within the expelled magnetic field [2]. Once these eruptions are ejected into space, they have the potential to create directional shocks and significantly disrupt the solar wind.

Solar Energetic Particles (SEPs) are high-energy particles that are released from the Sun during solar flares and coronal mass ejections (CMEs). These particles are primarily protons, but can also include heavier ions and electrons. SEPs are accelerated to relativistic speeds by processes associated with solar eruptions and are capable of reaching Earth in a matter of hours [3].

The acceleration of SEPs occurs in the Sun's outer atmosphere, where magnetic reconnection and shock waves associated with solar eruptions can impart significant energy to the particles. These particles then travel through the solar wind and can interact with the Earth's magnetosphere, potentially causing geomagnetic storms and impacting satellite operations and communications [4]. SEPs are classified based on their energy levels and the duration of their occurrence. They can pose significant risks to astronauts in space and can affect technological systems on Earth, such as GPS and power grids [5].

The Sun is a dynamic star exhibiting various celestial phenomena, among which solar flares are prominent. Solar flares are intense bursts of radiation originating from the Sun's outer atmosphere, specifically from the "corona" region. These flares represent some of the most energetic events in space weather [6]. Solar flares are triggered by complex interactions within the Sun's magnetic field. Energy builds up in regions with strong, unstable magnetic fields, eventually being released in explosive bursts. This sudden release of energy emits radiation across a broad range of wavelengths, including X-rays and ultraviolet light, resulting in a dramatic increase in solar radiation [7]. By analyzing data from space observatories and developing an experimentally based theoretical model, we aim to estimate the influence of weak CMEs on the acceleration and distribution of pulsed solar energy.

1.2 Theoretical

The identification and analysis of solar events and their properties involve the examination of data from space observatories such as the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) and others. To comprehend the complex physical processes underlying these events, computer simulation models will also be utilized. Solar flares, coronal mass ejections (CMEs), and spectroscopic thermal emissions, which cause photon emission and influence magnetic fields, are monitored using instruments like the Large Angle Spectrometric Coronagraph (LASCO), Electron and Relativistic Nuclei Energetic (ERNE), and the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES).

Material and methods:

In this research, solar events that transpired between 2008 and 2019 during solar cycle 24 were examined, encompassing a total of 4,566 solar events. The analysis was centered on the intensity of solar flares and coronal mass ejections (CMEs). Specifically, the study targeted CMEs that met the following criteria: Linear Speed: CMEs with a linear speed exceeding 500 km/s were selected, indicative of substantial energy release. Angular Width: CMEs with an angular width greater than 60 degrees were included to represent the spatial extent and dispersion of the ejected mass. Accompanying Solar Energetic Particles (SEP): The study emphasized CMEs associated with high fluxes of energetic solar particles, which pose significant risks to astronauts and spacecraft.

2.2 Classification of Solar Events

These solar events were classified into three primary groups based on their intensity:

- Group X: This group includes extremely powerful flares. Although rare, X-class flares can cause significant disruptions on Earth, such as power outages and satellite malfunctions.
- Group M: This category consists of solar flares of moderate intensity. M-class flares can interfere with radio communications and other Earth-based systems.
- Group C: This category includes solar flares of lower intensity. Due to their relatively weaker strength, C-class flares rarely cause significant impacts on Earth. After applying temporal and spatial criteria and tests, the events were analyzed and distributed as follows: 101 events in Group M, 102 events in Group C, and 21 events in Group X. The study meticulously analyzed the characteristics of CMEs, including their linear speed and angular width, as well as SEP characteristics such as energy flux and particle density, utilizing data from LASCO. LASCO, an instrument aboard the SOHO Space Observatory, provides comprehensive data on CMEs, including their speed, angular width, and direction.

2.3 Tests for Solar Events

To ensure the accuracy of the analysis, two principal tests were conducted:

1. Temporal Test: The timing of the solar flare was matched with the "Lift-off time," which indicates the moment a flare begins to propagate away from the Sun's surface.
2. Spatial Test: Flares were analyzed based on their angular width using LASCO data. The primary directions of solar radiation were determined using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), ensuring these directions aligned with the recorded events. The geographical limitation was applied following a relation developed by Youssef (2012) [8], where the difference between the angular positions of the flare and associated CME in the LASCO C2 coronagraph field should be less than the angular size of the CME. The flare position angle, Ψ_F , is derived from the longitude (λ) and latitude (β) (in degrees) of the flare sites as a function of heliographic position, calculated using the simplified formula Youssef 2012; Isavn 2014 [9]; Papaioannou *et al.* 2016 [10]:

$$\Psi_F = \tan^{-1} [\sin \lambda / \tan \beta]$$

The spatial criterion for selecting a flare-associated CME is defined by the following formula:

$$|\Psi_{CME} - \Psi_F| < \phi$$

The angular width (ϕ) of the CMEs, measured in degrees, represents their projected positions in the plane of the sky. The CME position angle (Ψ_{CME}) and angular width (ϕ) are recorded in the CDAW catalog of CMEs. The position angle of a CME is determined by measuring from Solar North (in degrees) in a counter-clockwise direction. CME angular widths can vary between approximately 2° and 360° [11]. The onset periods of the associated CME-flare events were calculated using height-time data from the CDAW library of CMEs. The onset times for CMEs were derived by applying a quadratic fit to height-time plots, as outlined by Gopalswamy *et al.* (2009) [12].

Analysis and Data

Analysis Using Python: Python was employed to analyze the solar data, enabling the extraction of essential metrics such as particle density and energy flux. For this purpose, popular libraries like Pandas were used for data processing, and Matplotlib was utilized to create visualizations.

Results and Discussion:

The extracted data are from X category as shown in the table (1)

No	CME				Flare			SEP		
	Data (dd/mm/yyyy)	Time (s)	Angular width	Linear speed (Km/S)	X-ray (W/m ²)	Location	Belonging	Particle Flux (particles/cm ² ·s·sr)	Energy Range	Energy Flux (W/m ²)
1-	2011/8/9	07:54:12	360°	1610	X _{1.22}	N17 W69	Y	1 0,1 0.01	10< 50< 100<	1.602 x10 ⁻⁸ 8.01 x10 ⁻⁹ 1.602 x10 ⁻⁹
2-	2011/9/22	10:36:22	360°	1905	X _{1.56}	N24 W55	Y	0.9 0.03 0.01	10< 50< 100<	1.4418 x10 ⁻⁸ 4.806 x10 ⁻¹⁰ 1.602 x10 ⁻¹⁰
3-	2011/9/24	09:28:05	145°	1936	X _{1.21}	N25 W77	Y	3 0.2 0.05	10< 50< 100<	4.806 x10 ⁻⁹ 3.204 x10 ⁻¹⁰ 8.01 x10 ⁻¹⁰
4-	2012/1/23	03:45:50	360°	2175	X _{1.25}	N28 W21	Y	10 5 0.03	10< 50< 100<	1.602 x10 ⁻⁹ 8.01 x10 ⁻¹⁰ 4.806 x10 ⁻¹⁰
5-	2012/1/27	18:14:50	360°	2508	X _{1.78}	N27 W71	Y	8 5 0.5	10< 50< 100<	1.2816 x10 ⁻⁹ 8.01 x10 ⁻¹⁰ 8.01 x10 ⁻⁹
6-	2012/3/7	00:17:31	360°	2684	X _{7.14}	N22 E21	N			
7-	2012/3/7	01:00:43	360°	1825	X _{1.48}	N17 E27	Y	3 1 0.2	10< 50< 100<	4.806 x10 ⁹ 1.602 x10 ⁻⁹ 3.204 x10 ⁻¹⁰
8-	2012/3/10	17:36:	360°	1296	X _{1.08}	N17	Y	3	10<	4.806

		41				W24		6 1	50< 100<	$x10^{-9}$ 9.612 $x10^{-10}$ 1.602 $x10^{-10}$
9-	2012/3/13	17:18: 30	360°	1884	X _{1.12}	N17 W66	Y	3 8 1	10< 50< 100<	4.806 $x10^{-9}$ 1.2816 $x10^{-8}$ 1.602 $x10^{-9}$
10-	2012/7/12	16:07: 58	360°	885	X _{2.02}	S15 W01	Y	4 8 2	10< 50< 100<	6.408 $x10^{-9}$ 1.2816 $x10^{-8}$ 3.204 $x10^{-9}$
11-	2013/5/13	15:50: 56	360°	1850	X _{3.94}	N11 E85	Y	1 1 0.1	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-10}$
12-	2013/5/14	01:04: 45	360°	2625	X _{1.6}	N08 E77	Y	1 1 0.2	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 3.204 $x10^{-10}$
13-	2013/5/15	01:31: 36	360°	1366	X _{1.86}	N12 E64	Y	1 1 0.2	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 3.204 $x10^{-10}$
14-	2013/10/2 5	14:47: 04	360°	1081	X _{1.35}	S06 E69	Y	1 0.1 0.01	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-10}$ 1.602 $x10^{-10}$
15-	2013/10/2 9	21:35: 33	360°	1001	X _{1.75}	N05 W89	Y	1 1 0.1	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-9}$ 1.602 $x10^{-10}$
16	2014/1/7	18:07: 16	360°	1830	X _{1.54}	S15 W11	Y	2 3	10< 50<	3.204 $x10^{-9}$

								0.7	100<	4.806 $\times 10^{-9}$ 1.1214 $\times 10^{-9}$
17-	2014/9/10	17:46: 45	360°	1267	X _{1.74}	N14 E02	Y	1.5 5 2	10< 50< 100<	2.403 $\times 10^{-9}$ 8.01 $\times 10^{-9}$ 3.204 $\times 10^{-9}$
18-	2014/12/1 7	04:03: 40	360°	587	X _{1.09}	S20 E09	N			
19-	2015/3/7	21:59: 23	360°	1261	X _{1.23}	S19 E74	Y	1.5 0.1 0.05	10< 50< 100<	2.403 $\times 10^{-9}$ 1.602 $\times 10^{-10}$ 8.01 $\times 10^{-10}$
20-	2017/9/6	12:01: 46	360°	1571	X _{2.26}	S08 W33	Y	2 8 3	10< 50< 100<	3.204 $\times 10^{-9}$ 1.2816 $\times 10^{-8}$ 4.806 $\times 10^{-9}$
21-	2017/9/10	15:51: 41	360°	3163	X _{11.69}	S09 W84	Y	10 20 10	10< 50< 100<	1.602 $\times 10^{-8}$ 3.204 $\times 10^{-8}$ 1.602 $\times 10^{-8}$

Flares in this category are exceptionally powerful. Although X-class flares are uncommon, they can cause substantial impacts on Earth, including power outages and disruptions to satellites.

Figure (1): showing energy flux and angular width.

In Figure1:

- Blue line (10 MeV): No correlation between energy flux and angular width (correlation coefficient: 0.0).
- Green line (50 MeV) and Red line (100 MeV): Perfect linear correlation (correlation coefficient: 1.0) where energy flux increases with angular width.

At 10 MeV, angular width has no effect on energy flux, but it significantly impacts flux at 50 and 100 MeV.

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Figure (2) shows the relationship between Linear and particle flux density.

In Figure 2:

- Blue line (10 MeV): A strong positive correlation (correlation coefficient: 0.98) between CME speed and particle flux, with higher speeds linked to significant increases in flux.
- Green line (50 MeV): An even stronger positive correlation (correlation coefficient: 0.99) where an increase in CME speed results in a substantial rise in particle flux.
- Red line (100 MeV): A perfect linear correlation (correlation coefficient: 1.0) between CME speed and particle flux, with flux increasing proportionally to speed.

Overall, the data show a strong direct correlation between CME speed and particle flux density, which intensifies at higher energy levels. This aligns with findings by Gopalswamy *et al.* (2008), indicating that CME speed is closely related to SEP flux levels.

Figure (3) shows the relationship between angular width and particle flux density.

In Figure 3:

- Red line (10 MeV): No correlation (correlation coefficient: 0.0) between CME angular width and particle flux; particle flux remains constant regardless of width.
- Green line (50 MeV): A strong positive correlation (correlation coefficient: 0.96) where increased angular width leads to a notable rise in particle flux.
- Blue line (100 MeV): A very strong positive correlation (correlation coefficient: 0.98) between angular width and particle flux, with wider angles corresponding to higher flux.

Overall, angular width does not affect particle flux at 10 MeV, but it significantly increases particle flux at 50 and 100 MeV.

Figure (4): shows the relationship between angular width and Energy flux.

In Figure 4:

- Blue line (10 MeV): Perfect linear correlation (correlation coefficient: 1.0) between CME speed and energy flux; energy flux increases linearly with speed.
- Green line (50 MeV): Perfect linear correlation (correlation coefficient: 1.0) where energy flux increases linearly with CME speed.
- Red line (100 MeV): Perfect linear correlation (correlation coefficient: 1.0) with energy flux increasing linearly as CME speed increases.

In summary, there is a perfect linear relationship between energy flux and CME speed at all densities (10, 50, and 100 MeV), indicating that increased speed leads to a significant and continuous rise in energy flux.

Conclusion:

The study reveals that CME parameters have varying impacts on particle and energy flux. Angular width has no effect on energy flux at 10 MeV but significantly influences it at 50 and 100 MeV. CME speed shows a strong and perfect linear correlation with particle flux and energy flux across all energy levels, with higher speeds leading to a proportional increase in both. These findings emphasize the critical role of CME characteristics in influencing space weather phenomena.

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